

solution these bodies assume the same form (*cf.* Rao and Jatkar, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, Allahabad, 1930, p. 225).

3. The heats of solution of two forms of triglycerides of trilaurin, tristearin and tripalmitin have been measured by the method of twin calorimeter.

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Dyes Derived from Acridic Acid.

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Acridic acid contains two carboxyl groups in *ortho* positions to one another, and is, therefore, expected to yield dyestuffs on condensation with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds in the same way as phthalic acid or quinolinic acid (Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102). Recently Tewari and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 58) have successfully condensed quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds with the production of dyestuffs having interesting properties of colour and fluorescence. They could not condense acridic acid itself on account of the fact that at that time it was practically an inaccessible material, but nevertheless from theoretical considerations they came to the conclusion that dyes derived from acridic acid, even if they could be prepared, would have the same colour as the corresponding dyes derived from quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid.

Acridine being now available in quantity, acridic acid was prepared from it by oxidation with potassium permanganate, and the acid condensed with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds in the usual manner with the production of dyestuffs. When compared with the corresponding dyes derived from quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid

it was found that the former class of dyestuffs are much more intensely coloured and far more absorptive than the latter. From this it is quite evident that the extra carboxyl in the dyes derived from quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acids acts as a bathochrome in reducing the intensity of colour and fluorescence. This fact will be quite apparent from the table of absorption maxima given at the end of the paper.

The following aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds have been condensed with acridic acid and the corresponding dyestuff obtained: phenol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol, hydroxyquinol, *m*-aminophenol, *m*-dimethylaminophenol, *m*-diethylaminophenol, orcinol and *m*-phenylenediamine. The compound with resorcinol has also been brominated and the corresponding tetrabromo derivative obtained. The condensation takes place without the use of any condensing agent, but the addition of a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid is beneficial in producing an increased yield of the dyestuff. In general properties these dyes resemble the corresponding phthaleins, but the intensity of colour is slightly more and the fluorescence slightly less. They dye wool and silk beautiful and brilliant shades.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of acridic acid.—10 G. of acridine were brought to a fine state of subdivision by solution in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitation with cold dilute caustic soda. The voluminous precipitate was collected, suspended in water and oxidised with a 2% solution of potassium permanganate. The mixture was heated to boiling and the permanganate added until it was no longer decolourised. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off first through cloth and then through paper, and the filtrate after being neutralised with hydrochloric acid was evaporated to a small volume and allowed to stand when a large amount of potassium chloride crystallised out. The filtrate on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid deposited the acridic acid gradually in crystalline crusts which were collected and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in stout prisms, *m. p.* 128-130° (decomp.).

The condensation of acridic acid with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds were effected in the same manner as in the case of quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid. For the sake of abbreviation, the results are given in tabular forms.

DYES DERIVED FROM ACRIDIC ACID

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TABLE I
(A = acridien).

Name.	Appearance.	M. p.	Colour in alcohol.	Colour with addition of acid or alkali	Shade on wool or silk.	Found.	Analysis Req.
Phenol-A	Yellow prisms	184°	Yellow	Crimson (Al)	---	C, 74.26 H, 4.3	74.8 4.06
Resorcinol-A	Brown crystalline powder	203°	Orange-yellow	Orange-red (Al)	Light orange	C 71.82 H, 3.36	72.06 3.39
Phloroglucinol-A	Brown yellow needles	above 280°	Orange-red	Blood-red (Al)	Light tan	N, 3.16	3.38
Hydroxyquinol-A	Brown powder	" "	Brown-red	Violet-red (Al)	Light violet	3.44	3.38
Orcinol-A	Dark brown needles	" "	Orange-yellow	Orange-red (Al)	Light brown	3.15	3.40
<i>m</i> -Aminophenol-A	Yellow-brown prisms	280°-285°	Brown-yellow	Brown-red (Ac)	Light chocolate	10.82	11.02
<i>m</i> -Dimethylamino-phenol-A	Pink needles	168°	Red	Crimson (Ac)	Bright pink	10.19	9.61
<i>m</i> -Diethylamino-phenol-A	"	120°	Dark-red	Crimson (Ac)	Deep pink	8.26	8.72
<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine-A	Brown crusts	295°	Yellow	Orange (Ac)	Chestnut	15.1	14.73
Tetrabromoresorcinol-A	Bright red prisms	above 290°	Bright pink	Crimson (Al)	Deep pink	Br, 45.22	45.78

TABLE II.

Absorption maxima of the acridcins and analogous dycstuffs.

Name.	-phthalein.	-quinolinein.	-cinchome- ronein.	-quinoline 1 :2 :3- tricarboxylein.	-acridien.
Phenol-	5540Å	5560Å	5520Å	5560Å	5880Å
Resorcinol-	4940	4950	4950	4930	5000
Phloroglucinol-	4980	4990	4980	4930	5055
<i>m</i> -Diethylami- nophenol-	5510	5540	5540	5540	5930
Tetrabromo- resorcinol-	5250	5250	5250	5180	5460

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A New Volumetric Method for the Estimation of Lead.

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Various methods have been proposed by different investigators for estimating lead volumetrically, the dichromate method being perhaps the most convenient. The object of the present paper is to describe a very simple and ready method for the estimation of lead volumetrically, in the absence of other metallic ions. It was found that neutral solutions of lead can be titrated with standard potassium sulphate solution, the end-point being determined by the use of fluorescein as an external indicator. In the concentrated solutions the end-point is quite sharp, the indicator (greenish-yellow) becoming vermilion-red in presence of Pb-ions. In dilute solutions the change in the colour of the indicator is not so sharp. With the decrease of the concentration of Pb-ions, the red colour gradually fades to a distinct yellow, which persists so long as Pb-ions are present.

Acid solutions of lead should be evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and the slight hydrolysis which might take place will not affect the result, as the solubility product of lead sulphate is much below that of the basic salt formed. The acid solutions cannot be